

PERSISTENT INDEBTEDNESS AMONG TEA PLANTATION LABOURERS IN PEERMADE IN THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT CONTEXT

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Abstract

Poverty is a depressing condition in which an individual or a family is unable to afford an adequate level of living in keeping with the society's standards. Despite several decades of progress of the plantation industry in our country, plantation labourers have remained less developed and isolated. Despite all legislative measures, plantation labourers are still marginalized and vulnerable. Their problems of low wages, ignorance on basic financial concepts and financial risk, indebtedness and poor financial health remain unaddressed and overlooked. The present study examines the situation of persistent indebtedness among tea plantation labourers in Peermade in the sustainable development context.

Key words: *tea plantation labourers, persistent indebtedness, sources of debt, quantum of debt, reasons for debt*

Introduction

Poverty means a circumstance of serious deprivation where a person lacks one or more basic need as opposed to a condition of inequality (Christopher, 2019). It is a depressing condition in which an individual or a family is unable to afford an adequate level of living in keeping with the society's standards. Absolute poverty is a life-threatening condition of deprivation of access to basic necessities of life such as food, shelter, clothing and health care (Francis, 2005). The poor die in young age and they usually suffer from communicable diseases,

maternal and perinatal conditions, and nutritional deficiencies. Unfortunately, in many communities, the most affected are women and children (Catherine & Sebean, 2017).

The principal plantation crops in Kerala economy namely tea, coffee, rubber and cardamom has an important share in the agriculture income of the state. Tea plantation labourers are undeniably as important to the plantation industry as producers, dealers and consumers. Despite several decades of progress of the plantation industry in our country, plantation labourers have remained less developed and isolated. The production and productivity of plantations depend heavily on the performance of the labourers employed therein and therefore, the welfare, morale and motivation of these labourers must be accorded importance. Despite all legislative measures, plantation labourers are still marginalized and vulnerable. Their problems of low wages, ignorance on basic financial concepts and financial risk, indebtedness and poor financial health remain unaddressed and overlooked. Hence the proposed study is highly relevant.

A very noticeable feature of the economic life of the tea plantation labourers in India is that they are generally in debt. This fact was referred to by various labour committees and commissions which were set up from time to time. The root cause of the evil is the want of any margin left for meeting the expenditure of an unforeseen character. It is true that one of the main causes of indebtedness is the expenditure incurred on marriage, funeral, etc. The worker is a part of a social organisation, and has perforce to conform to certain customary social standards even when he is not in a position to do so. The burden of debt passes on from generation to generation. The rural tea plantation labourers incur debts for nonproductive purposes such as to meet the family needs, perform social functions (related to marriages, birth, death), litigation, etc. Since money taken does not contribute to production but instead to consumption, it drags the rural tea plantation labourers into indebtedness. While borrowing money the borrower does not pay attention to his repaying capacity and for him even a little debt becomes a trap out of which he cannot come out.

Inclusive growth is an idea of economic growth that aims to improve the standard of living of a large group of population by reducing poverty and ensuring equal opportunity to all. Sustainable development is another idea to growth and human development that aims to meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of the future generations to meet their own

needs. In order to achieve this idea, the people at the grass root level should be brought under the formal financial channel as well as their situation of persistent indebtedness is to be properly addressed. Tea plantation labourers are not an exception to this.

Review of literature

The plantation workers have limited access to education or to economic opportunities to outside the plantations and therefore highly dependent on the employers. Working on plantations is far more than an eight to five job for millions of workers who depend upon the plantations for their hospitals, education, housing, etc (Kiran 2017). Tea garden workers are educationally lagging behind, health facilities are not adequate and safety measures are lacking (Parijat 2013). Tea garden labourers are still in very deprive condition and are far away from urbanized society and living an isolated life (Hazarika 2012).

Significance of the study

Plantation labourers are undeniably as important to the plantation industry and are still marginalized and vulnerable. Their problems of low wages, ignorance on basic financial concepts and financial risk, indebtedness and poor financial health remain unaddressed and overlooked. The proposed study will look these matters in detail and will bring into light the real status of the tea plantation labourers. The study is expected to drag the attention of general public, NGOs, government and financial institutions to take appropriate initiatives to address the problems of such labourers. Hence the study will be beneficial to such plantation society in the sense that they will get awareness about proper money management, official sources of credit, ways and means of coming out from debt, proper management of credit, and ways of improving financial health.

Often the tea plantation labourers are themselves not aware of the financial risks they face and the measures that need to be taken to avoid them besides lack of awareness. Poor labourers are unable to save for the social security schemes because they spend their income on meeting their more immediate survival needs, such as food, housing, education and healthcare for themselves and their families. Living from one day to next, they have differing social priorities, which keep them in a state of permanent indebtedness throughout their lives. Hence a

study on persistent indebtedness, financial health and financial literacy among tea plantation labourers in Kerala is found significant

Scope of the study

The focus of the study is limited to examine the socio-economic status of the tea plantation labourers, the income, expenditure, savings and investment patterns of such labourers, the situation of persistent indebtedness (in terms of level of borrowings, reasons for borrowings, sources of borrowings, and ability to repay), the root cause of persistent indebtedness among plantation labourers, The focus of the study will also be limited to the registered tea plantations in Peermade Taluk and the permanent tea labourers working in these plantations.

Objectives of the study

The study examines the situation of persistent indebtedness among tea plantation labourers in Peermade Taluk.

Methodology of the study

The study is descriptive but empirical in nature. Both secondary and primary data are sourced for the study. The secondary data are sourced from official publications, books and journals. Official websites are also be referred. The primary data are collected from the tea plantation labourers through multi-stage random sampling technique. At the first stage, the plantation grama Panchayaths are picked viz., Upputhara and Vandiperiyar. Then at the second stage the plantation in Peermade are divided into two categories (viz., large size and small size plantations) and then two plantations each from such categories are picked. Then at the third stage 50 plantation labourers each are picked from the above mentioned four plantations totaling 200 ($50 \times 4 = 200$) sample tea plantation labourers. A structured interview schedule was administered among these 200 tea plantation labourers. The interview schedule was finalized after the conduction of pilot survey and reliability analysis. Different tools like, simple percentages and Friedman's test are used for the analyzing of primary data.

Results and Discussions

Demographic profile of the respondents

The demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender, age, family size, number of dependents in the family and educational qualification represent in table below:

Table 1: Demographic profile of the respondents

Particulars		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	67	33.5
	Female	133	66.5
Age	Up to 20 years	34	17
	20-40 years	98	49
	40-60 years	68	34
Family size	Up to 3	27	13.5
	3 to 6	137	68.5
	Above 6	35	17.5
No .of dependents in the family	Up to 2	116	83
	2 to 4	43	21.5
	Above 4	41	20.5
Educational qualification	Illiterate	77	38.5
	Primary	66	33
	Secondary and above	57	28.5

Source: field survey

Table 1 above exhibits that most (66.5 percent) of the respondents are female who belong to the age group of '20 to 40 years' (49 percent). The family size of the majority (68.5 percent) is three to six members and have up to two dependents (83 percent) at home. Almost 39 percent of the respondents are illiterate and another 33 percent have only primary level of education.

Social profile

The social profile of the respondents viz., nature of house, land holding details and the color of ration card are as follows:

Table 2 : Social profile of the respondents

Particulars		Frequency	Percentage
Nature of house	Own house	38	19
	Estate lanes	141	70.5
	Labour quarters	21	10.5
Land holdings	Nil	155	77.5
	Up to 10 cents	28	14

	More than 10 cents	17	8.5
Colour of ration card	No card	76	38
	Yellow	53	26.5
	Pink	53	26.5
	Blue	12	6
	white	6	3

Source: field survey

Table 2 above exhibits that majority (70.5 percent) of the respondents live in estate lanes and have no land holdings (77.5 percent). It is to be noted that 38 percent of them have no ration card and another 26.5 percent (each) of them equally holds yellow and pink ration cards.

Economic profile

Table 3: Economic profile of the respondents

Particulars		Frequency	Percentage
Monthly household income	Up to 5000	43	21.5
	5000-10000	139	69.5
	Above 10000	18	9
Monthly household expenditure including loan repayment	Up to 4000	36	18
	4000 -8000	147	73.5
	Above 8000	17	8.5
Monthly savings	Nil (zero)	165	82.5
	Up to 2000	34	17
	2000 - 4000	1	05
Value of debt	Nil (zero)	13	6.5
	Up to 25000	86	43
	25000 – 50000	73	36.5
	Above 50000	28	14

Source: Field survey

From table 3 it is crystal clear that majority (69.5 percent) of them earns in between Rs. 5000 and Rs. 10000 and expends in between Rs. 4000 and Rs. 8000 in a month (73.5 percent). Many of them do not have any savings (82.5 percent) and a good number have debt of up to Rs.25000. Another 36.5 percent have debt in between Rs.25000 and Rs.50000.

Sources of debt, value of debt and purposes of debt

Sources of debt

In order to identify the most common sources of debt of the sample tea plantation labourers, eight variables were included in the interview schedule and the responses were gathered on a five point scale. Thereafter Friedman's test has been administered to identify

common the sources of debt. The hypothesis formulated towards this end and the test result are as follows:

Ho: There is no significant difference between the mean rank of the responses towards various sources of debt of the respondents.

Ha: There is significant difference between the mean rank of the responses towards various sources of debt of the respondents.

Table 4: Sources of debt

<i>Sources of debt</i>	<i>Mean rank</i>	<i>Chi-square value</i>	<i>p-value</i>
1. Borrowings from friends/relatives	4.74	1381.29 (df:5)	<0.001**
2. Borrowings from SHG/JLG	6.73		
3. Borrowings from private indigenous money lenders	6.81		
4. Borrowings from micro credit institutions like ESAF	5.58		
5. Borrowings from non-banking finance companies	5.22		
6. Borrowings from banks	4.12		

Source: Field survey

From table .. it is clear that the most dominant sources of debt of tea plantation labourers include borrowings from private indigenous money lenders (mean =6.81), borrowings from SHG/JLG (mean rank = 6.73), and borrowings from micro credit institutions like ESAF (mean rank=5.58). Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Quantum of debt

The quantum of debt of the sample tea plantation labourers from different sources are analysed with simple percentage. The sources considered are i) pledging of ornaments, ii) borrowings from SHG/JLG, iii) money lenders, iv) ESAF, and v) NBFC. The result is presented in the following table.

Table 5: Quantum of debt

Sources		Quantum of Debt			
		Up to 25000	25000 - 50000	Above 50000	Total
Pledging ornaments	Frequency	43	68	7	118
	percentage	36.44	57.62	5.93	100
Debt from SHG/JLG	Frequency	98	36	42	176
	percentage	55.68	20.45	23.86	100

Debt from Money lenders	Frequency	48	93	39	180
	percentage	26.66	51.66	21.66	100
Debt from ESAF	Frequency	89	65	0	154
	percentage	57.79	42.20	0	100
Debt from NBFC	Frequency	6	12	64	82
	percentage	7.31	14.63	78.04	100

Source: field survey

As far as the pledging of ornaments is concerned, more than half (57.62 percent) of the sample tea plantation labourers get loan in between 25000 and 50000 rupees. But regarding the debt from SHG /JLG is concerned, again more than half (55.68 percent) of them have debt up to 25000.

As far as the debt from money lenders are concerned, 51.66 percent of them borrow in between 25000 and 50000. But 57.79 percent of them borrow up to 25000 from ESAF. It is to be noted that 78.04 percent of them have debt over Rs.50000 from NBFCs.

Purposes of debt

In order to identify the most significant purposes to which the respondents borrow, eight variables were included and the responses were gathered on a five point scale. Thereafter Friedman's test has been administered to identify common the sources of debt. The hypothesis formulated towards this end and the test result are as follows:

Ho: There is no significant difference between the mean rank of the responses towards the purposes of debt of the respondents.

Ha: There is significant difference between the mean rank of the responses towards the purposes of debt of the respondents.

Table 6: Purposes of debt

<i>Purposes of debt</i>	<i>Mean rank</i>	<i>Chi-square value</i>	<i>p-value</i>
1. To meet day to day living expenses	8.05		
2. To meet emergency hospital expenses	8.82		
3. To meet education expenses of the children	6.72		
4. To meet the marriage expenses of daughter	6.98		

5. To meet emergency fund requirements like meeting funeral expenses, well digging etc.	3.62	1285.14 (df:7)	<0.001**
6. To meet the expenses of constructing/purchasing a house	6.70		
7. To purchase a vehicle/land	4.58		
8. To pay off another debt	6.12		

Source: field survey

Note: ** denotes significant at one percent level

From table 6, it is clear that the most common purposes of debt of the tea plantation labourers are meeting emergency hospital expenses (mean rank = 8.82), meeting day to day living expenses (mean rank = 8.05), and meeting marriage expenses of daughter (mean rank=5.58). Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Reasons for indebtedness

In order to identify the most significant reasons for indebtedness sixteen variables were included and the responses were gathered on a five point scale. Thereafter Friedman's test has been administered to identify most common reasons for indebtedness. The hypothesis formulated towards this end and the test result are as follows:

Ho: There is no significant difference between the mean rank of the responses towards the reasons for indebtedness of the respondents.

Ha: There is significant difference between the mean rank of the responses towards the reasons for indebtedness of the respondents.

Table 7: Reasons for indebtedness

<i>Reasons for indebtedness</i>	<i>Mean rank</i>	<i>Chi-square value</i>	<i>p-value</i>
1. Personal loans	21.53		
2. Reduced family income/increased family expenditure	26.03		
3. Inflation	26.03		
4. Medical expenses	25.45		
5. No family budget/ participatory decision making	26.67		
6. Bad habits in life	15.81		
7. Poor financial inclusion	19.07		
8. High personal expenditure	25.83		
9. Purchase of household luxuries	26.83		

10. Poverty	21.79	4302.31(df-15)	<0.001**
11. Ignorance and illiteracy	22.25		
12. No savings/investments/insurance	27.19		
13. Absence of transparency of earnings by family members	22.77		
14. Multiple/ cross borrowings	27.26		
15. Unproductive and wasteful expenditure of loan	26.98		
16. My ancestral debt	17.04		

Source: field survey

Note: ** denotes significant at one percent level

From table 7, it is clear that the most common reasons for indebtedness of the tea plantation labourers are multiple or cross borrowings (mean rank=27.26), no savings/investments/insurance (mean rank = 27.19), unproductive or wasteful expenditure on loan (mean rank=26.98), no family budget/participatory decision making (mean rank =26.67) and purchase of household luxuries (mean rank=26.83). Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion

Achievement of cent percent of inclusive growth and sustainable development is possible only by considering the marginalized and disadvantaged sections of the society. Still 43 percent of the people in our country are not in a position to have three round meals a day. In this context, the study results are an eye opener to the policy makers and the authority concerned. Still, the tea plantation labourers are unable to come out of their persistent indebtedness and come under formal financial channels. Many of them have no savings and a good number have debt. Their sources of debt are from indigenous money lenders, SHGs and micro credit institutions. They have a debt in between 25000 and 50000 from gold pledging, up to 25000 debt from SHG and have debt in between 25000 and 50000 from money lenders, up to 25000 from ESAF and over 50000 from NBFCs. They borrow for emergency hospital expenses, day to day living expenses and for the marriage of their female children. Reasons for indebtedness are multiple /cross borrowings, no savings / investments/insurances, unproductive spending of loan amount and nonfamily budget and participatory decision making. In order to tackle such issue, financial literacy centres are to be opened at plantation locality as well as the services of business correspondents or facilitators are to be offered at such locality. The services of Mahila Pradhan agent is also to be ensured at such locality. More deliberate but constructive measures are to be effected to uplift such tea plantation worker community and to genuinely bring them out from indebtedness and under formal financial channels and thereby to achieve real inclusive growth and sustainable development.

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